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Transformation for Rural Development: An analysis of Perspective Transformation of Participants of a VET Course in Agriculture

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Abstract

Context: Sustainable rural development depends on how swiftly new knowledge, and practices are accepted, adopted, and implemented and formal, non-formal and/or informal vocational training opportunities designed specifically for agriculture sector can cater for much needed knowledge transfer. This study is situated in such a context; through a qualitative methodology, it aims to explore to what extent the implementation of a modular pilot vocational education and training (VET) programme is effective in terms of fostering a “perspective transformation” towards adoption of better, novel, and innovative practices in agriculture (Mezirow, 1991, 2000).

Approach: In order to determine whether the participant farmers experienced a perspective transformation, the Learning Activities Survey and Follow-up Interview Form developed by King (1997) were employed as data collection tools. The study group consisted of practising farmers (n=16) who have successfully attended and completed at least two modules of the programme.

Findings: As a result of the data analysis, the PT Index Scores reveal that the majority of the participants (n=12) have experienced a perspective transformation as a result of the training they have received. The majority of participants (n=10) who have experienced a perspective transformation have noted that it was induced because of the unconventional approach of the delivery of courses. A total of 11 participants revealed that the field visits were effective for their experience of transformation while one participant informed that the transformation was induced during classroom discussions with peer farmers.

Conclusion: This study aims to identify and discuss the efficiency of a modular pilot VET programme in agriculture that is designed and targeted to meet the identified needs of farming community in northern part of Cyprus for adoption of better practices. The results of this study can be useful for a broad range of stakeholders that are active in agricultural sector; education and training institutions that deliver agricultural training, agricultural policymakers aiming for sustainable rural development practices, educational practitioners and/or consultants active in the sector, vocational education, and training authorities as well as curriculum developers.

Keywords: VET in agriculture, transformative learning theory, perspective transformation, lifelong learning, rural development

1 Introduction

There is no shortage of challenges that dominate the agriculture sector today, and incessant flow and implementation of knowledge and innovation are necessary to cope with these challenges if successful rural development is targeted. Rural development is a multifaceted process and comprises variables such as sustainable production, natural resource management, policy-

making and institutional decision-making, climate change, infrastructure, finance, and education and training, each of which confronts distinct challenges on its own (Maalouf, 1988; Maguire, 2000). This calls for new skill sets even for experienced and trained farmers, and ordain efficient use of resources, sustainable production methods through best practices, action against climate change and integration of innovation and new technologies. At the core of rural development, agriculture is a knowledge and research-intensive area. It is critical that the farmers, as key stakeholders for rural development, receive, accept, and implement innovation and knowledge at the same pace these are produced.

However, the flow of knowledge in agricultural sciences is top-down, hence positioning information and new knowledge at an abstract status. Traditional and conventional approaches to the transfer of agricultural knowledge often fail to meet agricultural practitioners' real needs on the field (Lioutas, 2019). Also, new, research-based knowledge is not always readily available for the farming community which relies heavily on empirical practical experience. 2017 European Parliament briefing by Augère-Granier indicates that only 8.5 % of the present generation of European farmers are qualified with a degree in agriculture whereas as much as 70 % rely solely on practical experience which does not qualify as verifiable vocational training (2017).

In such a context, whether already practising members of the farming community or the aspiring younger generation, vocational education and training (VET) and lifelong continuous professional development are crucial for farmers. Here, lifelong learning emerges as a prospect to help farmers of various ages and educational backgrounds gain new knowledge, skills, and competences that are necessary to capitalise from if balanced dynamics for rural development is targeted. Sustainable rural development depends on how swiftly these practices are adopted and implemented. Therefore, as much as making the new knowledge and skills ready for the farming community, internalisation and adoption of these are critical. It is important to track, enquire and follow up on how and to what extent this new knowledge and information is internalised and utilised by the recipient farming community.

2 Theoretical Framework

One approach to take on to enquire whether introduction of new knowledge and skills have resulted in construction of new ways of thinking and doing is to employ the lens of transformative learning theory (Anderson et al, 2018; Galt et al., 2013; Parr & Trexler, 2011). An attempt to assess agricultural training from such lens may provide answers in multiple aspects. First it may serve to understand if a proposed vocational and technical curriculum could challenge, and shift farmers' set of habitual views, schemas, and structures of belief in their own conventional and traditional practices. Secondly, since transformative learning theory builds on experiences in formal, non-formal and/or informal educational settings as sources for perspective transformation, such assessment may present evidence whether the proposed curricula provide effective experiential instances to induce perspective change.

Transformative learning theory has foundations associated with a wide variety of philosophical and psychological theories and approaches; Kuhn's (1962) concept of philosophical paradigm, psychoanalytic theory (Dirkx, 1998; Kitchenham, 2008; Mezirow, 1978a), constructivist approach, Freire's (1970) concept of conscientization and Habermas's (1971, 1984) domains of learning and types of knowledge (Ari, 2015; Calleja, 2014; Dirkx, 1998; Kitchenham, 2008). For Mezirow (2000, 1991, 1997), transformative learning theory focuses on people's meaning-making processes. Therefore, transformative learning is a process that enables individuals to become more inclusive, open, emotionally sensitive, and reflective so that they can form beliefs and ideas that can guide their actions in a more real and reasonable way. In one sense, the theory is about how individuals form and act on their own objectives, values, feelings, and meanings, rather than assumptions they acquire from others without the filter of critical

consideration, so that they can have more say in their lives as socially responsible, open-minded decision-makers (Mezirow, 2000).

In a similar line, Cranton (2016) states that her definition of the foundations of transformative learning is based on this first definition of Mezirow; transformative learning is a process in which assumptions, beliefs, values, and perspectives that have not been critically evaluated before are questioned, thereby making those assumptions, beliefs, values, and perspectives more open, permeable, and better justified. In its simplest form, Mezirow (2003) defines transformative learning as the process of individual's understanding and knowing himself or herself. This process should lead to changes in the way the individual sees himself/herself, the world, and his/her own experiences, and ultimately differentiate his/her general perspective.

According to transformative learning theory, experiences play a central role in adult learning. When the individual brings the new knowledge, he/she has acquired through experiences to the awareness of his consciousness, he enters a reflection process about how this new knowledge is compatible with existing belief, value structures and ways of being/doing. If the new information is compatible with the past beliefs and value structures, the individual continues his/her life without any change in these patterns and does not make any transformative changes. However, suppose this new information that comes to the consciousness of the individual through experience does not fit into the older patterns and schemas acquired in the past. In that case, a process of harmonisation and balancing begins between the new conflicting information and the existing beliefs and values, initiated by questioning the beliefs, values, and assumptions about what this incompatible piece is. From time to time, the new knowledge gained in this balancing process prevails, and a new perspective begins to take root in the individual (King, 2009; Mezirow, 1997). Mezirow (1995) describes these “changing events in our lives can make us feel that old meaning perspectives have become dysfunctional” and “that no matter how much harder we try, things do not seem to fit old ways of seeing any longer” (p. 44). The whole cycle of this process is defined as perspective transformation and can be considered as the transformation of meaning structures acquired by individuals throughout their lives (Mezirow, 1991, 1997, 2003).

Transformative learning theory describes adult learning as the intentional acquisition of an individual's beliefs, values, and assumptions through a critical reflection process as a result of an experience in formal or non-formal educational environments and/or informally in life. In this context, Mezirow (1991, 2000) defines perspective transformation as a ten-stage process that includes cognitive dimensions such as exploration, evaluation, self-examination and planning as part of the learning experience (Senyshyn, 2018). Therefore, perspective transformation is the structural transformation of the individual's perception of himself/herself and his/her relationships with the world (Mezirow, 1978b). Mezirow's perspective transformation has been defined in his previous works as steps, phases or stages leading to a transformation that begins with a disorienting dilemma and ends in a state of regained equilibrium (Mezirow, 1991, 1994).

However, Cranton (2002) also states that in most of the later research on transformative learning theory, although many of these steps of the process have remained in one way or another, they are no longer seen as linear steps to be followed definitively. In this study, perspective transformation is handled as a process consisting of ten transformation phases as revealed by Mezirow (1991, 2000) as follows:

1. Disorienting dilemma / 2. Self-examination / 3. Critical assessment / 4. Recognition of shared experiences/ 5. Exploring options for new behaviour / 6. Planning a course of action / 7. Acquisition of knowledge / 8. Trying new roles / 9. Building confidence / 10. Reintegration

Although these phases outline a linear direction for perspective transformation, an individual might still experience perspective transformation and still assess himself/herself to have gone

through only the first few stages. This is why Cranton (2002) states that transformative learning is not a linear process. However, it can have a circular structure.

As discussed above, assessing recipient farmers' experiences from the lens of transformative learning theory may serve to understand whether the implemented educational intervention challenged and shifted the farmers' old and dysfunctional patterns of thought, belief, and practices or not. Therefore, this study attempts to explore to what extent the pilot implementation of a vocational and technical curriculum that is designed and developed by an EU Technical Assistance Project tasked with the Implementation of Farm Advisory Services (FAS) in northern part of Cyprus is effective in terms of fostering a "perspective transformation" towards adoption of better, novel, and innovative practices in agriculture (Mezirow, 1991, 2000). In this context, this study aims to analyse the effect of a pilot modular VET programme in agriculture on participant farmers' perspective transformation towards adoption of better practices in agriculture and seeks to answer the following research questions:

- I. Was the pilot modular VET programme in agriculture effective to induce perspective transformation of farmers towards adoption of better practices in agriculture?
- II. How do farmers describe their experience of perspective transformation through the implementation of a modular VET programme in agriculture?
- III. In which phases, as defined by Mezirow (1991, 2000) this perspective transformation has occurred?
- IV. Which element of the pilot VET programme has facilitated this perspective transformation?

3 Methodology

This study employs a qualitative methodology to explore the experiences and views of participant farmers to the pilot modular VET programme in agriculture. In order to determine whether the participant farmers experienced a perspective transformation towards the adoption of better practices in agriculture as a result of the implemented VET curriculum, the Learning Activities Survey (LAS) and Follow-up Interview Form (King, 1997) were employed as data collection tools. The survey was also used to determine at which dimensions the farmers have experienced the perspective transformation as defined by Mezirow (1991, 2000) and to identify the activities that contributed to this transformation. The data analysis is conducted as per guidelines by King (2009) and the Perspective Transformation (PT) Index score obtained by the participants determine whether the farmers have experienced the perspective transformation or not. The qualitative analysis of the Follow-up Interview Forms provides a deeper understanding of the experience of farmers. The translation and adaptation of both instruments which are developed by King (1997) were completed by the researcher as per previous approval by King.

3.1 Study Group

The study group consists of a total of 16 practising farmers who have attended and successfully completed at least two modules of the VET programme in agriculture. A total of eight participants are female while the remaining eight are male. The farmers could opt for any of the eight thematic modules based on their area of production and/or interest as long as they complete the obligatory, cross-cutting module on Introduction to Farm Management. All the farmers in the study group have completed the cross-cutting Introduction to Farm Management module. Following the completion of this obligatory module, a total of five participants completed Advanced Beekeeping, seven have completed Sheep and Goat Herd Management and four have completed Dairy Cattle Herd Management modules.

3.2 Pilot VET Programme in Agriculture

The modular pilot VET programme in agriculture is designed, developed, and implemented by the EU Technical Assistance Project, tasked with the Implementation of Farm Advisory Services (FAS) in northern part of Cyprus. The design, development and delivery of the training is conducted under the task of provision of advice and providing technical assistance to farmers which are two of the many tasks of the project. The proposed VET curriculum was based on the needs analysis that was also conducted by the experts engaged by FAS project. The needs analysis conducted by the project revealed that effective education and vocational training opportunities were not available for farmers. The farmers were offered limited, scattered, and short-term ad-hoc courses organised by either NGOs or other institutions which mostly fail to generate a longer-lasting effect on adoption of better agricultural practices. In such a context, design, development and implementation of a standardised vocational education and training course for both crop and livestock production with a strong component in farm management practices was deemed critical for rural development in northern part of Cyprus.

The modular curriculum was designed to be compatible with the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) and consisted of eight thematic modules based on the results and priority areas outlined following the needs analysis. The delivery methods of the modules included both theoretical and practical sessions with an emphasis on the practical aspect of agricultural practices for both crop and livestock production. The duration, hours of theoretical and practical sessions of each module varied based on the content. The thematic modules were as follows:

1. Introduction to Farm Management (28 hours, basic, obligatory)
2. Citrus Growing (32 hours, advanced, elective)
3. Olive Growing (32 hours, advanced, elective)
4. Advanced Beekeeping (28 hours, advanced, elective)
5. Dairy Cattle Herd Management (32 hours, advanced, elective)
6. Sheep and Goat Herd Management (36 hours, advanced, elective)
5. Organic Agriculture (26 hours, advanced, elective)
6. Advanced Organic Agriculture (32 hours, advanced, elective)

Each thematic unit was organised in a varying number of Learning Units (LUs) which lasted for four hours and corresponded to one session so that the participation of farmers was ensured. The LUs were structured to deliver a corresponding set of Learning Outcomes (LOs), which were pre-defined in terms of knowledge, skills, and competences which the farmers would be able to apply in his/her own professional context. The objectives for best agricultural practices in the EU such as natural resources management, efficient use of resources, soil management, better animal welfare, hygienic practices to attain food safety at farm level, conscious use of pesticides and other chemicals in the farm, occupational health, and safety and others comprised an intrinsic part of all the thematic modules to direct participant farmers to implementation of standard that were close to the EU.

In order to ensure complete participation of the farmers, the maximum allowed number of participants to each module was limited to 15 trainees. All the content was developed by the experts engaged by FAS project in accordance with the identified LUs and LOs. The language of instruction and training materials were Turkish, and all the sessions were delivered by experts engaged by FAS project. The modules were delivered in accordance with the seasonality of the theme to ensure that the practical demonstrations and activities could be carried out in the right period (e.g. exercise of olive pruning and harvesting should be done in November; honey harvesting in spring/summer etc.). The scheduling of the thematic modules was organised respecting farmers' daily and seasonal workload; in such a timeframe when farmers were able to successfully attend the courses (e.g. livestock breeders were not engaged in lessons in

the morning or late afternoon because they would be busy milking animals, etc.). The participants could choose to attend one or more modules depending on their area of production and/or interest. Upon full attendance and successful completion of the courses the participants received a certificate of achievement signed by relevant Turkish Cypriot bodies responsible for agriculture and education.

3.3 Data Collection Tool, Data Collection Process and Data Analysis

The data collection tools employed to identify whether the modular pilot VET programme in agriculture was effective to induce perspective transformation of the participant farmers were Learning Activities Survey (LAS) and Follow-up Interview Form developed by King (1997). The LAS was developed in 1997 by Cathleen P. King who was one of the leading researchers of transformative learning theory. King (1997) states that the two main purpose of LAS are (i) to determine whether there is a perspective transformation in relation to the educational experience and, if so, (ii) to determine which learning activities conducted contributed to this transformation. King (1997) defines perspective transformation as central to learning in the context of andragogy. She developed LAS based on the need for a better understanding of perspective transformation, which is both an integral part of adult learning and essential for the realisation of transformative learning, considering the lack of tools to enable empirical evaluation of perspective transformation in the literature. Transformational learning theory (Mezirow, 1978a, 1978b) forms the theoretical basis of LAS, and there are two major reasons to employ LAS and Follow-Up Interview Form as the data collection tools in this study. First of all, the curriculum objectives developed are related to the changes that farmers will experience in the acquisition of knowledge and skills for better practices. These changes, which are expected to be experienced in form of competence, habitual ways of thinking and doing are related to the practices carried out during the educational activities and the experiences of the participants regarding these practices.

LAS provides an opportunity to understand what these activities are, what kind of classroom experience the farmers have had, and what their reflections include. In addition to this, the survey also reveals if the farmers experienced a perspective transformation and if they did, it also reveals at what phase this had happened. LAS also provides information on whether the factors that initiated this transformation are related to classroom experience or other dynamics effective in life. Thus, the researcher can clearly identify whether the source of the participant's perspective transformation is directly related to educational activities and practices. LAS consists of 14 questions in which quantitative and qualitative data were collected, and the Follow-up Interview Form consists of eight questions in which only qualitative data were collected. As a data collection tool, the optional, closed-ended, and open-ended questions in the entire survey are intended to determine whether the participants have experienced a transformation in perspective. The validity and reliability of the instrument were conducted by King (1997).

The data collection process was completed over a six-week period following the certification of the farmers based on voluntary participation. Necessary approvals have been obtained from authorities of FAS project to feature the participant group as sample. The farmers were first asked to fill LAS. The scoring criterion for LAS is a composite score, which is defined by King (1997) as the Perspective Transformation Index/PT Index and consists of the answers to questions 1, 2, 3 and 5 in the first part of the survey. The PT Index is presented as the criterion score. If the participants experienced a transformation related to the training they received, the PT-Index is stated as PT-Index=3, if the transformation they had experienced which was not directly related with the training they received, PT-Index is stated as PT-Index=2, and if they had experienced perspective transformation at all PT-Index is stated as PT-Index=1.

Upon first analysis of the data, the participants who revealed a perspective transformation had been contacted again to conduct follow-up interviews in order to obtain in-depth

understanding of their experience. These interviews were recorded and then transcribed for coding. The coding process was completed by the researcher. There are different approaches to ensure the reliability of coding, and intercoder reliability can be calculated in various ways (Cohen, 1960; Krippendorff, 1980; Miles & Huberman, 1994; Scott, 1955). In this study, in order to ensure coding reliability, the similarities and differences of the codes obtained from the data set were compared numerically by using a single approach in the analysis of qualitative data. This technique, which is based on numerical comparison of codes determined by different coders and understanding whether similar codes are used or not, is defined as intercoder reliability by Miles and Huberman (1994). According to this, "intercoder reliability can be calculated by dividing the number of agreed codes by the total number of agreed and non-agreed codes" (Arastaman et al., 2018) Yıldırım and Şimşek (2016) state that a reliability percentage of at least 70 % should be achieved in such studies. Miles and Huberman (1994) suggest that an initial rate of 70 % is acceptable, but it should be close to 90 % depending on the size of the dataset. However, Miles and Huberman (1994) stated that an agreement of 80 % on 95 % of the codes among different coders is sufficient for intercoder reliability. For this purpose, the interview transcripts, which were taken randomly from data set to form 80 % of the data set, were coded by another researcher other than the researcher, and the reliability was calculated by dividing the number of agreed codes by the sum of the number of agreed and disagreed codes and multiplying by 100 ($[\text{Consensus}/(\text{Disagreement}+\text{Consensus})]*100$). Accordingly, the reliability rate of 83 % was reached and it was accepted that the reliability of the coding was ensured due to the intercoder reliability being over 70 % (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016).

3.4 Researcher's position

The researcher was not engaged in any of the processes of development, design, and delivery of the training programme. This had ensured complete neutrality in terms of the results obtained. The content and the views presented in this study are those of the researcher alone. They do not in any way represent the official opinion of the European Union.

4 Findings

As a result of the data analysis, the majority of the participants (n=12) scored with a PT-Index=3. This finding reveals that a total of 12 participant farmers were challenged by the training provided and experienced a shift in their existing belief, view and practice schemas and structures. This finding is significant in terms of the capacity and potential of the content, delivery methods and overall structure of the pilot VET programme to change conventional, habitual ways of doing and initiate internalisation of new knowledge and skills towards better and more sustainable practices in agriculture. The embedded objectives to attain best agricultural practices similar to the ones in the EU such as natural resources management, efficient use of resources, soil management, better animal welfare, hygienic practices to attain food safety at farm level, conscious use of pesticides and other chemicals in the farm, occupational health, and safety and others had an impact on the participant farmers to have a perspective transformation and caused them to change their ways of thinking and doing.

Among those participants who have experienced a perspective transformation a total of 10 have noted that it was induced because of the unconventional approach of the delivery of courses. During follow-up interviews they further detailed this as the distribution of theoretical and practical sessions throughout the courses. The practical sessions which were conducted as field and farm visits were noted as the most effective means to initiate the change in participant farmers perspectives. One of the farmers who have experienced perspective transformation revealed that this was induced during discussions with peer farmers during one of the classroom sessions. Among other statement the farmers indicated that they were "impressed by the farm

visits”, “learned new ways of managing the farm”, “realised the importance of bookkeeping” and “gained new knowledge”.

5 Conclusion

This study aims to explore and discuss the effectiveness of a modular pilot VET programme in agriculture that is developed to meet specific needs of farmers in northern part of Cyprus. The implementation of the systematised pilot VET programme included unconventional methods such as practical field and farm visits, discussion sessions and demonstrations. The results obtained from this study is informative for a diverse group of actors that are involved in rural development work and studies. These can be listed as training institutions involved in delivery of agricultural training, policymakers, educational practitioners, farm advisors, farmers, and other agricultural practitioners. The findings of the study reveal that farmers can shift and change their previous perceptions, beliefs, ways of thinking and doing through effective educational experiences.

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